

A Novel Approach to the Continuous Planting and Harvest Scheduling

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Among all food chain losses, post-harvest handling and storage losses are among the most prominent, particularly in less developed countries. Farmers with limited storage and processing capabilities could substantially reduce their yield overflows and consequent unnecessary waste by adopting continuous harvest strategies. Nowadays, the increase in average farmland and the number of crop varieties opens additional room for continuous harvest. However, common planting and harvesting planning practices typically treat each parcel of land in isolation, missing the opportunity of a more integrated approach that would equalize the expected yield during the harvest period, while performing harvest activities in a reduced number of weeks.

We designed an algorithmic core of an integrated decision support system tailored to assist farmers in managing their planting and harvesting activities. This algorithmic core is a composition of the three scheduling algorithms and one weather forecast processing algorithm. With their synergy, the designed system would generate schedules that facilitate continuous harvest, with crops harvested at their optimal maturity. Furthermore, the system enables dynamic adjustment of harvesting schedules based on actual weather conditions on the fields, thereby enhancing schedule reliability and introducing stability into further operational planning. Our initial results indicate that with the generated harvest schedules it is possible to reduce the total amount of yield exceeding stated storage and processing capacities.

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